

PPDR: A Privacy-Preserving Dual Reputation Management Scheme in Vehicle Platoon

Yuxin Sun, Zhiquan Liu, Yingjie Xia, Zhen Guo, Gao Liu, Leping Li, and Jianfeng Ma

Abstract—Vehicle platoon has attracted much attention in recent years for its benefits in improving traffic efficiency, road safety, and energy consumption. In a vehicle platoon, vehicles can take on the roles of either a leading vehicle or a following vehicle, depending on the need. Selecting a reliable leading vehicle is crucial to improve the reliability of the vehicle platoon, and reputation management plays a vital role in this selection process. However, the existing reputation management schemes do not distinguish the leading vehicle’s reputation value (LV-Reputation value) and the following vehicle’s reputation value (FV-Reputation value), and merge them into a single reputation value, which exposes the reputation management scheme to the single reputation attack, an attack identified for the first time in this work. Additionally, some schemes fail to preserve the vehicle reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, or identity privacy, and some overlook the security of the reputation management scheme. To address these issues, we propose a Privacy-Preserving Dual Reputation (PPDR) management scheme in vehicle platoon. The PPDR scheme separates a vehicle’s reputation value into LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value, effectively mitigating the single reputation attack. Furthermore, under the premise of preserving reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, the PPDR scheme employs a score difference calculation algorithm to support the weighted average mechanism and the dual reputation

management mechanism, which can significantly improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme. It also provides strong security with acceptable computation communication overheads. Comprehensive theoretical analysis and simulation evaluation have been carried out, and the results demonstrate that the PPDR scheme is significantly superior than the existing schemes in several aspects.

Index Terms—Vehicle platoon, dual reputation management, privacy preservation, reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, identity privacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, vehicle platoon has attracted much attention due to its advantages in enhancing traffic efficiency, improving road safety, and reducing energy consumption [1], [2], [3]. In a vehicle platoon, one vehicle is selected as the leading vehicle, while the others act as the following vehicles [4], [5], [6]. As the leading vehicle is crucial for controlling the vehicle platoon, its proper selection is key to maintaining vehicle platoon reliability [7], [8], [9].

To ensure the trustworthiness of the leading vehicle, reputation management schemes are proposed to evaluate the reliability of vehicle and identify potential malicious vehicles [2], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Since each vehicle in the vehicle platoon can act as either a leading vehicle or a following vehicle when needed, reputation evaluations should distinguish the reputation values of the two roles. However, most existing schemes adopt the single reputation management mechanism, which merges the leading vehicle’s reputation value (LV-Reputation value) and following vehicle’s reputation value (FV-Reputation value) into a single reputation value [2], [13]. However, this mechanism ignores the functional distinctions between the leading vehicle and the following vehicle. As a result, the adversary may exploit it by providing high-quality service as a leading vehicle to maintain a high reputation value, while submitting malicious feedback score as a following vehicle. Conversely, it might submit honest feedback score as a following vehicle but providing low-quality service as a leading vehicle. We designate this attack as the Single Reputation Attack.

To further illustrate the concept of the single reputation attack, Fig. 1 provides a simplified explanation. Suppose there are four vehicles, labeled vehicle A, vehicle B, vehicle C, and vehicle D. Vehicle A is the adversary, while the others are trustworthy. ‘1’ represents a positive feedback score submitted from the following vehicle to the leading vehicle, while ‘-1’ represents a negative feedback score.

As shown in Fig. 1(a), at time t , vehicle A serves as a leading vehicle and behaves honestly, receiving positive

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Fig. 1: Two scenarios for the single reputation attack, i.e. (a) vehicle A acts as an honest leading vehicle and acts as a malicious following vehicle, and (b) vehicle A acts as an honest following vehicle and acts as a malicious leading vehicle (where ‘1’ represents a positive feedback score submitted from the following vehicle to the leading vehicle, while ‘-1’ represents a negative feedback score. Vehicle A is the adversary, while vehicle B, vehicle C, and vehicle D are honest vehicles).

feedback from the other vehicles, and thereby accumulating a high reputation score. However, at time $t + \Delta t$, A acts as a following vehicle and submits malicious feedback scores, which undermines the accuracy of the reputation management scheme. Similarly, as shown in Fig. 1(b), at time t , A acts as a following vehicle, providing honest feedback scores, and thereby accumulating a high reputation score. However, at time $t + \Delta t$, A abuses its position by delivering low-quality service or making unsafe decisions.

The dual reputation management mechanism by separate reputation values into LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value, can effectively resist the single reputation attack, and significantly improves the accuracy of the reputation management scheme.

However, reputation management involves numerous operations, including data collection, decryption, and verification. Relying solely on a trusted authority (TA) to execute these operations may lead to substantial computation and communication overheads, and even makes the TA become the bottleneck of the reputation management scheme [13], [15]. Cloud computing, with its on-demand computing and storage resources, has been leveraged to significantly enhance the performance of reputation management scheme in vehicle platoon. However, the honest-but-curious property of the cloud leads to a variety of privacy challenges in vehicle platoon [16], [17].

If the vehicle identity privacy is not preserved, the adversary may track the vehicle’s movements and infer sensitive information about its driver [3]. If the reputation value privacy is not preserved, the adversary could launch a reputation link attack by associating reputation information with vehicle identity [18]. Furthermore, if the feedback score privacy is not preserved, the authenticity of feedback score could be undermined, especially in situation where there is fear of retaliation, which undoubtedly reduce the accuracy of reputation management scheme.

Moreover, the large, open, and highly dynamic nature of vehicle platoon leads to a variety of security challenges as the

adversary may launch the forgery attack, tampering attack, replay attack, and Sybil attack [3].

To resist the single reputation attack, preserve vehicle privacy, and improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme with acceptable computation and communication overheads, we propose a novel Privacy-Preserving Dual Reputation (PPDR) management scheme in vehicle platoon based on Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) [19] and Paillier [20] algorithms. The major contributions of this work are as follows.

- This paper reveals the single reputation attack for the first time, and it proposes a novel PPDR management scheme. Specifically, under the premise of preserving reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, the PPDR scheme employs a score difference calculation algorithm to support weighted average mechanism and dual reputation management mechanism, which can resist the single reputation attack and significantly improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme.
- The PPDR scheme provides strong privacy preservation for the vehicle identity, LV-Reputation value, FV-Reputation value, and feedback score. Additionally, it can resist the forgery attack, tampering attack, replay attack, and Sybil attack.
- This work conducts comprehensive theoretical analysis and simulation evaluation, and the results demonstrate that the PPDR scheme is significantly superior than existing schemes in several aspects.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews some related work, and Section III introduces the related preliminaries. Then, Section IV introduces the system model, attack model, and design goals. Section V details the various stages in the PPDR scheme. In Section VI and Section VII, theoretical analysis and simulation evaluation are carried out, respectively. Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Vehicle platoon is an innovative driving mode that can significantly enhance traffic efficiency, improve road safety,

and reduce energy consumption [21], [22], [23]. In a vehicle platoon, each vehicle in the vehicle platoon can act as either a leading vehicle or a following vehicle when needed [24]. The leading vehicle is responsible for controlling the vehicle platoon, including its speed and direction, while the remaining vehicles act as the following vehicles [10], [11]. Therefore, selecting an honest leading vehicle is crucial for ensuring the reliability of the vehicle platoon [25], [26]. Reputation management plays a vital role in this process, as it can help assess the reliability of the leading vehicle. Consequently, numerous reputation management schemes have been proposed for vehicle platoon in recent years.

In [13], Cheng et al. proposed a privacy-preserving protocol for vehicle feedback, named the PPVF scheme, which uses Paillier encryption to preserve feedback score privacy. However, the scheme adopts the simple average mechanism instead of the weighted average mechanism, causing feedback scores from malicious following vehicles to be treated with the same weight as those from honest following vehicles [3]. Moreover, it only supports the single reputation management mechanism. These limitations significantly compromise the accuracy of the reputation management scheme.

To preserve the reputation value privacy and identity privacy with support the weighted average mechanism, in [2], Li et al. proposed a reputation-based and privacy-preserving platoon management scheme, named the RPPM scheme, which adopts the weighted average mechanism to update the leading vehicle's reputation value. All reputation values are encrypted with Paillier by vehicles. Afterwards, the Cloud Service Provider (CSP) aggregates these ciphertexts and submits the aggregated ciphertexts to the TA. However, the TA cannot obtain each individual feedback score submitted from each following vehicle, thus it cannot evaluate the reliability of each following vehicle. In [3], Liu et al. proposed a privacy-preserving reputation updating scheme, named the PPRU scheme, which also adopted the weighted average mechanism to update the leading vehicle's reputation value. In this scheme, following vehicles submit encrypted feedback scores, and the CSP calculates a weighted average of the feedback scores, with the reputation values as the weights. However, since the scheme is not specifically designed for the vehicle platoon, it fails to distinguish the LV-Reputation value and the FV-Reputation value (i.e. adopts the single reputation management mechanism), which makes it vulnerable to the single reputation attack, and reduces the overall accuracy of reputation management scheme.

To improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme, in [10], Hu et al. proposed an honest trust-based platoon service recommendation scheme, namely the REPLACE scheme, which adopts an iterative filtering algorithm to update the leading vehicle's reputation value. This algorithm calculates the trust scores of following vehicles, and a weighted average mechanism is then adopted to update the leading vehicle's reputation value, effectively excluding following vehicles that submit malicious feedback scores. In [12], Wu et al. proposed an energy-efficient and trust-based formation algorithm for cooperative vehicle platoon, which combines feedback scores with a trust updating algorithm to update the leading vehicle's reputation value. However, these schemes do not preserve

the reputation value privacy, making them vulnerable to the reputation link attack. Additionally, they fail to preserve the feedback score privacy, leaving the following vehicles apt to submit untrue feedback scores due to fear of retaliation [2]. Also, they do not support batch verification.

To achieve batch verification and preserve identity privacy, in [14], Zhang et al. proposed a trust-based and privacy-preserving platoon recommendation scheme, namely the TPR scheme. Although the scheme anonymizes the vehicle identity, it does not consider the preservation of reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy. Moreover, it uses time-consuming bilinear pairing. In [27], Xu et al. proposed an efficient and multi-dimensional privacy-preserving platoon communication scheme in vehicular networks. This scheme comprehensively considers reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, but it does not take into account the update of the FV-Reputation value. That is, the dual reputation management mechanism was not considered in this scheme.

To ensure the preservation of reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, enhance the accuracy of reputation management scheme, and address the limitations of above schemes with acceptable computation and communication overheads, we propose a novel PPDR scheme in this paper, and the intuitive property comparisons with the existing schemes are shown in Table I. From Table I, it is evident that the PPDR scheme is significantly superior than the existing schemes in several aspects.

III. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we mainly introduce two important preliminaries involved in the PPDR scheme, namely ECC and Paillier algorithms.

A. ECC Algorithm

The ECC algorithm provides enhanced security with shorter key length compared to other asymmetric cryptographic methods [19], [28]. Specifically, the ECC algorithm consists of three main stages [3], [29].

Key Generation: Using a selected prime number p to define a finite field Z_p , an elliptic curve $y^2 \equiv x^3 + ax + b \pmod{p}$ is established with $a, b \in F_p$ satisfying $4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$. All the points in the elliptic curve with the infinity point forms an additive cyclic group \mathbb{P} with a q -order generator P . Given P and a random number $s \in Z_q^*$, the point $S = s \cdot P \in \mathbb{P}$ can be computed efficiently within the group \mathbb{P} . However, given P and a random point $S \in \mathbb{P}$, it is computationally infeasible to determine $s \in Z_q^*$ that satisfies $S = s \cdot P$ in probabilistic polynomial time, which is known as the Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP) assumption [30]. Consequently, the ECC public key is S and the ECC private key is s .

Encryption: For a plaintext $m \in \{0, 1\}^*$ and an ECC public key S , the m is firstly transformed into $M \in \mathbb{P}$. The ciphertext is then generated as $C = (r \cdot P, M + r \cdot S)$, where r is a random number, and $r \in Z_q^*$. Clearly, $C \in \mathbb{P} \times \mathbb{P}$.

TABLE I: An intuitive property comparisons with the existing schemes.

Properties	[2]	[3]	[10]	[12]	[13]	[14]	[27]	Ours
Weighted average	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓
Dual reputation management	×	×	✓	✓	×	✓	×	✓
Reputation value privacy	✓	✓	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓
Feedback score privacy	×	✓	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓
Identity privacy	✓	✓	×	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bilinear pairing-free	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×	✓	✓
Batch verification	✓	✓	×	×	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: ✓ and × denote support and nonsupport, respectively.

Decryption: For a ciphertext C and an ECC private key s , the C 's plaintext can be recovered by using the equation $(M + r \cdot S) - s \cdot (r \cdot P) = M$, and then M is decoded to m .

B. Paillier Algorithm

The Paillier algorithm offers a more efficient additive homomorphic function compared to other homomorphic algorithms [20]. Specifically, the Paillier algorithm consists of following three key stages [3], [13], [14].

Key Generation: Choose two random large prime numbers p and q satisfying $\gcd(p \cdot q, (p - 1) \cdot (q - 1)) = 1$, $n = p \cdot q$ and $\lambda = \text{lcm}(p - 1, q - 1)$ are calculated, where $\gcd(x, y)$ and $\text{lcm}(x, y)$ denote the greatest common divisor and least common multiple of two numbers x and y , respectively. Then, select a random value $g \in \mathbb{Z}_{n^2}^*$ that satisfies $\gcd(\mathcal{L}(g^\lambda \bmod n^2), n) = 1$, where $\mathcal{L}(x) = \frac{x-1}{n}$. As a result, the Paillier public key and Paillier private key are (n, g) and (λ, μ) , respectively, where $\mu = \mathcal{L}(g^\lambda \bmod n^2)^{-1} \bmod n$.

Encryption: For a plaintext $m \in \mathbb{Z}_n$ and a Paillier public key (n, g) , the m 's ciphertext is computed as $\text{Enc}(m) = g^m \cdot (r')^n \bmod n^2$, where r' is randomly chosen from \mathbb{Z}_q^* . Clearly, it is evident that $\text{Enc}(m) \in \mathbb{Z}_{n^2}^*$.

Decryption: For a ciphertext c and a Paillier private key (λ, μ) , the c 's plaintext can be recovered by using $\text{Dec}(c) = \mathcal{L}(c^\lambda \bmod n^2) \cdot \mu \bmod n$.

In addition, for $\forall m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_n$, the Paillier algorithm has the following two homomorphic properties.

$$\text{Enc}(m_1 + m_2) = \text{Enc}(m_1) \cdot \text{Enc}(m_2) \bmod n^2. \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Enc}(m_1 \cdot m_2) = (\text{Enc}(m_1))^{m_2} \bmod n^2. \quad (2)$$

IV. SYSTEM MODEL, ATTACK MODEL, AND DESIGN GOALS

In this section, we first introduce the system model, attack model, and design goals of the PPDR scheme.

A. System Model

As shown in Fig. 2, the PPDR scheme consists of four kinds of main entities, namely a Trust Authority (TA), a Cloud Service Provider (CSP), Roadside Units (RSUs), and vehicles. The details of these entities are as follows.

1) *TA*: The TA initializes the ECC and Paillier cryptosystems. Moreover, it generates public key and private key for the TA, CSP, and generates main public key and main private key for the vehicles. It also generates pseudonym and the

corresponding temporary public key and temporary private key for each vehicle. Additionally, it participates in calculating the LV-Reputation value and the FV-Reputation value. Besides, it is equipped with a clock.

2) *CSP*: The CSP is equipped with powerful computing and storage capabilities. Moreover, it assists in calculating the LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value. The CSP also has a clock that is synchronized with the TA. Additionally, the CSP has a secure wired channel with the TA.

3) *RSUs*: The RSUs are installed on the side of road and serve as communication relays between vehicles and the upper entities, namely the TA and the CSP. They play a crucial role in facilitating communication in the reputation management scheme.

4) *Vehicles*: Each vehicle is equipped with a clock that is synchronized with the TA's clock, an On-Board Unit (OBU), and a Trusted Platform Module (TPM). In the PPDR scheme, each vehicle can undertake two alternative roles, namely leading vehicle and following vehicle.

- **Leading Vehicle (LV)**: In a vehicle platoon, the leading vehicle is responsible for controlling the vehicle platoon, including its speed and direction. Moreover, we define the LV-Reputation to evaluate its reliability when the vehicle leads the vehicle platoon as a leading vehicle.
- **Following Vehicle (FV)**: In a vehicle platoon, all the vehicles except the leading vehicle are considered to be following vehicles. Additionally, we define the FV-Reputation to evaluate their reliability when the vehicle submits feedback score as a following vehicle.

B. Attack Model

In this part, we analyze the potential threats to the TA, CSP, RSUs, and vehicles in the PPDR scheme.

Similar to many recent studies [2], [13], the TA is assumed to be fully reliable. The CSP and RSUs are considered honest-but-curious, which implies that they will strictly execute their preassigned roles, yet they may attempt to retrieve private information regarding the vehicles. For instance, they may seek to obtain the vehicle identity, LV-Reputation value, FV-Reputation value, and feedback score. In addition, similar to many recent studies [2], [3], we do not consider the collusion attack.

Moreover, we assume that the majority of vehicles are honest, but the other vehicles are malicious. Specifically, in the PPDR scheme, during the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages, a malicious vehicle may forge

Fig. 2: System architecture of the PPDR scheme.

its FV-Reputation value or its pseudonym (i.e., conduct the forgery attack), tamper with other following vehicle's feedback score or other leading vehicle's pseudonym (i.e., conduct the tampering attack), submit an outdated feedback message (i.e., conduct the replay attack), or submit multiple feedback messages for the same feedback target in a short period of time by adopting multiple pseudonyms (i.e., conduct the Sybil attack).

C. Design Goals

The design goals of the PPDR scheme consist of strong privacy preservation, strong security, and accurate reputation management with acceptable computation and communication overheads.

1) *Strong Privacy Preservation*: During the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages, the PPDR scheme should provide strong privacy preservation, meaning that the vehicle identity, LV-Reputation value, FV-Reputation value, and feedback score should not be revealed or linked by the adversary.

2) *Strong Security*: During the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages, the PPDR scheme should be capable of resisting several common attacks within the vehicle platoon, such as the forgery attack, tampering attack, replay attack, and Sybil attack.

3) *Accurate Reputation Management*: To provide accurate reputation management, the PPDR scheme should support the weighted average mechanism for feedback score ciphertexts, as the weighted average mechanism is far more effective than the simple average mechanism in mitigating the impact of malicious feedback scores. Additionally, the PPDR scheme should support the dual reputation management mechanism to resist the single reputation attack and improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme.

4) *Acceptable Computation and Communication Overheads*: The PPDR scheme should support the batch verification of signatures and avoid the utilization of time-consuming bilinear pairing, with achieve acceptable computation and communication overheads.

V. VARIOUS STAGES IN THE PPDR SCHEME

A. Initialization

When the PPDR scheme is deployed in vehicle platoon, the TA and the CSP synchronize their respective clocks. Subsequently, the TA initializes the ECC and Paillier cryptosystems, as described in Section III. The TA generates the Paillier public key (n, g) and the Paillier private key (λ, μ) . After that, the TA defines four hash functions as $h_1: \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q^*$, $h_2: \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ and $h_3: \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q^*$. Then, the TA chooses a random number $SK_{TA} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ as its private key, and generates the corresponding public key $PK_{TA} = SK_{TA} \cdot P$. Similarly, the TA selects another random number $SK_{CSP} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ as the CSP's private key, and the CSP's public key is generated as $PK_{CSP} = SK_{CSP} \cdot P$. Finally, the TA publishes the system parameters $\langle p, q, P, \mathbb{P}, PK_{TA}, PK_{CSP}, h_1(\cdot), h_2(\cdot), h_3(\cdot), (n, g) \rangle$, and transmits the private key SK_{CSP} to the CSP through a secure channel.

In addition, the RSUs are installed on the side of road. Then, RSUs serve as the relays for the communication between vehicles and the upper entities, namely the TA and the CSP.

B. Vehicle Registration

Inspired by [31], when a new vehicle is registered with the TA, the TA first assigns the vehicle a real identifier OID_i . For ease of illustration, we denote the vehicle as V_i . Similarly, V_j refers to a vehicle with a real identifier OID_j .

To resist the single reputation attack, we separate each vehicle's reputation value into LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value.

Inspired by [32], [33], [34], the TA initializes the LV-Reputation value r_i^L for vehicle V_i based on its category, as depicted in Eq. (3).

$$r_i^L = \begin{cases} \lceil 0.9 \cdot \eta_1 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a law enforcement vehicle,} \\ \lceil 0.5 \cdot \eta_1 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a public service vehicle,} \\ \lceil 0.1 \cdot \eta_1 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a private vehicle.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where η_1 is a scaling factor that controls the range of LV-Reputation value, and $\lceil \# \rceil$ denotes the result of rounding up $\#$.

Similarly, the TA initializes the FV-Reputation value r_i^F for vehicle V_i based on its category, as depicted in Eq. (4).

$$r_i^F = \begin{cases} \lceil 0.9 \cdot \eta_2 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a law enforcement vehicle,} \\ \lceil 0.5 \cdot \eta_2 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a public service vehicle,} \\ \lceil 0.1 \cdot \eta_2 \rceil, & \text{if } V_i \text{ is a private vehicle.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where η_2 is a scaling factor that controls the range of FV-Reputation value.

Then the TA selects a random number $SK_{V_i} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ as the V_i 's main private key, and the V_i 's public key is generated as

$PK_{V_i} = SK_{V_i} \cdot P$. Subsequently, the TA transmits the registration message $M_1 = \langle OID_i, PK_{V_i}, SK_{V_i}, r_i^L, r_i^F, t_1 \rangle$ to the V_i through a secure channel, where t_1 represents the timestamp. The vehicle's TPM and the TA record the M_1 , respectively.

C. Vehicle Pseudonym Update

When a vehicle V_i intends to obtain or update its pseudonym, it randomly selects a number $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ and computes $AID_{i,1} = \alpha_i \cdot P$. Subsequently, V_i sends a request message $M_2 = \langle OID_i, AID_{i,1}, t_2 \rangle$ to the TA via a secure channel, where OID_i denotes V_i 's real identify, t_2 denotes the timestamp (it can be achieved using hybrid encryption method [35], due to space limitations, this paper will not repeat). Upon receiving M_2 , the TA verifies that OID_i exists. The detailed introduction is in [3]. This content is omitted as it is beyond the scope of this paper. Then the TA computes $AID_{i,2} = OID_i \oplus h_1(SK_{TA} \cdot AID_{i,1} \| PK_{TA})$. Consequently, the V_i 's pseudonym is defined as $AID_i = \{AID_{i,1}, AID_{i,2}, T_i\}$, where T_i is the timestamp. Next, the TA calculates $\beta_i = h_2(AID_i \| PK_{TA})$, randomly selects a number $\theta_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$, and computes the temporary public key as $PK_i = \theta_i \cdot P$. The temporary private key is then computed as $SK_i = (\beta_i + \theta_i) \cdot (SK_{TA})^{-1} \bmod q$. Finally, the TA packages the temporary public key PK_i , the temporary private key SK_i , and the pseudonym AID_i into a response message M_3 , that is, $M_3 = \langle OID_i, PK_i, SK_i, AID_i, t_3 \rangle$, where t_3 denotes the timestamp. The TA securely transmits M_3 to V_i by using a hybrid encryption method. Furthermore, we can also divide time into discrete intervals and adopt the same approach as [3] to prevent repeated acquisition of a pseudonym, temporary public key, and temporary private key from the TA.

D. Vehicle Platoon Formation

When the vehicle V_j intends to apply for becoming the leading vehicle, it must submit the basis leading message to the CSP, including its pseudonym AID_j , departure address N_d^j , and arrival address N_a^j . Upon approval, V_j becomes the leading vehicle, and the CSP broadcasts the basis platoon message, which includes AID_j , N_d^j , and N_a^j . For ease of description, the formed vehicle platoon is denoted as H .

Note that the communication channels between vehicles and the CSP are insecure. Therefore, all transmitted messages, whether from leading vehicles or following vehicles, must be encrypted and signed. Detailed encryption, signing, or other details of the vehicle platoon formation process can be found in [2], [36], [37], and are omitted here due to space limitations.

If the vehicle V_i wants to join the vehicle platoon H , it must submit the basis following message to the CSP by using the same encryption and signing method. The message includes the pseudonym of the target leading vehicle AID_j , its own pseudonym AID_i , its departure address N_d^i , and arrival address N_a^i . Upon approval, the CSP generates an entry certificate $P_{i,j,k} = (k, AID_i, AID_j, b_k)$, where k represents

the order that the vehicle joins the vehicle platoon. Inspired by [32], the value of b_k is calculated as Eq. (5).

$$b_k = 2 \cdot x_{max} \cdot \sum_{k'=1}^{k-1} b_{k'} + 1. \quad (5)$$

where $b_1 = 1$, and x_{max} represents the upper limit of feedback score.

Note that, for clarity in the subsequent analysis, we denote the pseudonym AID_i of the following vehicle V_i as $AID_{i,k}$. That is, $AID_{i,k}$ is entirely equivalent to AID_i , and $P_{i,j,k} = (k, AID_{i,k}, AID_j, b_k)$. Similarly, we denote the FV-Reputation value r_i^F of the following vehicle V_i as $r_{i,k}^F$.

After generation, the CSP returns $P_{i,j,k}$ to the V_i (it also need be encrypted and signed). Next, the V_i 's TPM and the CSP store $P_{i,j,k}$, respectively.

E. Feedback Score Submission

Upon the completion of its journey, the following vehicle V_i is obligated to submit a feedback message for the leading vehicle V_j to the CSP. To this end, the V_i 's TPM first generates a feedback score $x_k \in [0, x_{max}]$. Based on this score, the TPM computes two ciphertexts as $C_k = g^{x_k \cdot r_{i,k}^F} \cdot (r_i)^n \bmod n^2$ and $C'_k = g^{x_k \cdot b_k} \cdot (r_i')^n \bmod n^2$, where $r_{i,k}^F$ denotes V_i 's FV-Reputation value, b_k is derived from its entry certificate $P_{i,j,k}$, and $r_i, r_i' \in \mathbb{Z}_{n^2}^*$ are randomly chosen values. Subsequently, the TPM computes $\eta_{i,j,k} = h_3(C_k \| C'_k \| P_{i,j,k} \| PK_i \| t_4)$, where $P_{i,j,k}$ represents its entry certificate, PK_i represents its temporary public key, and t_4 represents the timestamp. A random value $\gamma_{i,j,k} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$ is then selected, $Y_{i,j,k} = \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA}$, and $\mu_{i,j,k} = SK_i + \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k} \bmod q$ can be calculated. Finally, the TPM generates the signature $\sigma_{i,j,k} = (Y_{i,j,k}, \mu_{i,j,k})$ and sends the feedback message $M_4 = \langle C_k, C'_k, P_{i,j,k}, PK_i, t_4, \sigma_{i,j,k} \rangle$ to the CSP.

When the CSP receives the M_4 , it queries the corresponding vehicle platoon based on the leading vehicle V_j 's pseudonym AID_j , and retrieves the associated b_k (obviously, the CSP can obtain the $k, AID_{i,k}, AID_j$, and b_k from $P_{i,j,k}$). If all queries are successful, the CSP verifies whether Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) hold. Eq. (6) is used to verify the freshness of M_4 , while Eq. (7) is used to check whether the vehicle has submitted feedback messages for multiple times by using the same entry certificate.

$$t' - t_4 \leq \Delta t'. \quad (6)$$

$$k \notin P_j. \quad (7)$$

Here, t' denotes the timestamp when the M_4 is received by the CSP, $\Delta t'$ denotes the preset tolerable transmission delay, and P_j denotes the set of k currently received.

If Eq. (6) or Eq. (7) is not satisfied, the CSP discards M_4 ; otherwise, the CSP proceeds to verify the signature of M_4 . The CSP calculates $R_{i,j,k} = Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}$, where $\eta_{i,j,k} = h_3(C_k \| C'_k \| P_{i,j,k} \| PK_i \| t_4)$. If Eq. (8) holds, M_4 is accepted; otherwise, it is discarded.

$$\mu_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA} = h_2(AID_{i,k} \| PK_{TA}) \cdot P + PK_i + R_{i,j,k}. \quad (8)$$

The proof of correctness of Eq. (8) is shown as Eq. (9).

$$\mu_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA} = (SK_i + \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}) \cdot PK_{TA}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= SK_i \cdot PK_{TA} + \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA} \\
&= (\beta_i + \theta_i) \cdot (SK_{TA})^{-1} \cdot PK_{TA} + R_{i,j,k} \\
&= (\beta_i + \theta_i) \cdot P + R_{i,j,k} \\
&= h_2(AID_{i,k} || PK_{TA}) \cdot P + PK_i + R_{i,j,k}. \tag{9}
\end{aligned}$$

In addition to the one-by-one verification described above, the CSP can also perform batch verification for multiple signatures via Eq. (10). It is assumed that the vehicle platoon includes K following vehicles ($K \geq 1$), each of which is involved in the batch verification.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{i,j,k} \right) \cdot PK_{TA} \\
&= \left(\sum_{k=1}^K h_2(AID_{i,k} || PK_{TA}) \right) \cdot P + \sum_{k=1}^K PK_i + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{i,j,k}. \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

The proof of correctness of Eq. (10) is shown as Eq. (11).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\sum_{k=1}^K \mu_{i,j,k} \right) \cdot PK_{TA} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K (SK_i + \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}) \cdot PK_{TA} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K SK_i \cdot PK_{TA} + \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K (\beta_i + \theta_i) \cdot (SK_{TA})^{-1} \cdot PK_{TA} + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{i,j,k} \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K (\beta_i + \theta_i) \cdot P + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{i,j,k} \\
&= \left(\sum_{k=1}^K h_2(AID_{i,k} || PK_{TA}) \right) \cdot P + \sum_{k=1}^K PK_i + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{i,j,k}. \tag{11}
\end{aligned}$$

After the verification passes, the CSP adds k to P_j . Utilizing the homomorphic properties of the Paillier cryptosystem, via Eq. (12) and Eq. (13), the CSP obtains two aggregation results, G_K^R and $G_K^{R'}$, for C_k and C'_k , respectively. Additionally, the CSP calculates the sum G_K^b from b_1 to b_K via Eq. (14).

$$G_K^R = \prod_{k=1}^K C_k. \tag{12}$$

$$G_K^{R'} = \prod_{k=1}^K C'_k. \tag{13}$$

$$G_K^b = \sum_{k=1}^K b_k. \tag{14}$$

Subsequently, the CSP transmits the aggregated message $M_5 = \langle G_K^R, G_K^{R'}, G_K^b, \{AID_{i,k}\}_{k=1}^K, AID_j \rangle$ to the TA through a secure channel.

F. Reputation Value Update

After receiving the M_5 , the TA first queries the FV-Reputation value of each following vehicle from the database based on their pseudonyms and then calculates the aggregated FV-Reputation value r_{all}^F via Eq. (15).

$$r_{all}^F = \sum_{k=1}^K r_{i,k}^F. \tag{15}$$

Then the TA decrypts G_K^R as $Dec(G_K^R)$ and calculates the incremental reputation value M_j of the leading vehicle V_j via Eq. (16).

$$\begin{aligned}
M_j &= \lceil Dec(G_K^R) / r_{all}^F \rceil \\
&= \lceil \frac{Dec(\prod_{k=1}^K C_k)}{\sum_{k=1}^K r_{i,k}^F} \rceil \\
&= \lceil \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K x_k \cdot r_{i,k}^F}{\sum_{k=1}^K r_{i,k}^F} \rceil. \tag{16}
\end{aligned}$$

where $Dec(\cdot)$ represents the Paillier decryption function.

Next, the TA calculates the updated LV-Reputation value $r_j^{L'}$ of leading vehicle V_j via Eq. (17).

$$r_j^{L'} = r_j^L \cdot \rho + M_j \cdot \varepsilon \cdot (1 - \rho). \tag{17}$$

where r_j^L represents the current LV-Reputation value of leading vehicle V_j , retrieved from the database by the TA, ρ represents a system parameter, and ε represents a scaling factor. The output $r_j^{L'}$ is confined to the range $[0, \eta_1]$.

Subsequently, the TA encrypts the updated LV-Reputation value and sends it back to the leading vehicle via the RSUs by using a hybrid encryption method. Afterwards, the vehicle's TPM updates the LV-Reputation value accordingly. The detailed introduction is in [3], [38]. This content is omitted as it is beyond the scope of this paper.

Next, the TA decrypts $G_K^{R'}$ as $Dec(G_K^{R'})$, and calculates S_j via Eq. (18). Note that, the S_j will be utilized by the CSP to determine the difference between the vehicles' feedback scores and the incremental reputation value in the subsequent process. This operation aims to reduce the TA's computation overhead, and ensure the feedback scores privacy and incremental reputation value privacy, as the CSP is an honest-but-curious entity.

$$\begin{aligned}
S_j &= G_K^b \cdot (x_{max} - M_j) + Dec(G_K^{R'}) \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K b_k \cdot (x_{max} - M_j) + \sum_{k=1}^K x_k \cdot b_k \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^K b_k \cdot (x_{max} - M_j + x_k). \tag{18}
\end{aligned}$$

Then the TA returns S_j to the CSP through a secure channel.

Upon receiving S_j , the CSP sorts the M_4 of each following vehicle in ascending order according to k . The CSP then calculates $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K\}$ via Algorithm 1, where $D_k = x_{max} - M_j + x_k$.

Note that, as described in the vehicle platoon formation stage, each following vehicle has a one-to-one correspondence

with its entry certificate. Therefore, it is straightforward for the CSP to associate D_k with the vehicle V_i . Specifically, initially, s_K is set to S_j (line 1). Then, for each following vehicle, the CSP calculates D_i iteratively (lines 2-5). Finally, s_1/b_1 is assigned to D_1 (line 6), and the algorithm terminates at line 7. After that, the CSP stores $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K\}$ (the algorithm correctness proof is discussed in Section VI.F).

Algorithm 1 Score difference calculation algorithm.

Input: $\{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_K\}, S_j$
Output: $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K\}$

- 1: set $s_K = S_j$
- 2: for $k = K$ to 2 do
- 3: $s_{k-1} = s_k \bmod b_k$
- 4: $D_k = \frac{s_k - s_{k-1}}{b_k}$
- 5: end for
- 6: $D_1 = \frac{s_1}{b_1}$
- 7: return $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K\}$.

Therefore, upon the completion of Algorithm 1, the CSP generates the evaluation value E_k^i for each following vehicle V_i via Eq. (19).

$$E_k^i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (-th_1 + x_{max}) \leq D_k \leq (th_1 + x_{max}), \\ -1, & \text{if } D_k > x_{max} + th_2 \text{ or } D_k < x_{max} - th_2, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where th_1 is the reward threshold, and th_2 is the penalty threshold ($0 \leq th_1 \leq th_2 \leq x_{max}$). When D_k satisfies $(-th_1 + x_{max}) \leq D_k \leq (th_1 + x_{max})$, which indicates that the deviation between the feedback score and the incremental reputation value is less than the reward threshold, as a result, the FV-Reputation value increases. When D_k satisfies $D_k > x_{max} + th_2$ or $D_k < x_{max} - th_2$, which indicates that the deviation between the feedback score and the incremental reputation value exceeds the penalty threshold, as a result, the FV-Reputation value decreases. If none of these conditions are met, the FV-Reputation value remains unchanged.

The CSP sends the evaluation message $M_{10} = \langle \{E_k^i\}_{k=1}^K \rangle$ to the TA through a secure channel. Subsequently, the TA calculates the updated FV-Reputation value $r_i^{F'}$ of following vehicle V_i via Eq. (20).

$$r_i^{F'} = \min(\max(r_{i,k}^F + E_k^i \cdot \varepsilon', 0), \eta_2). \quad (20)$$

where r_i^F represents the current FV-Reputation value of V_i , retrieved from the database by the TA, and ε' represents a system parameter. The output $r_i^{F'}$ is confined to the range $[0, \eta_2]$.

The TA then encrypts the updated FV-Reputation values and transmits them to the corresponding following vehicles through the RSUs by using the same hybrid encryption method as it transmits LV-Reputation value to the leading vehicle. The vehicle's TPM updates the FV-Reputation value accordingly.

VI. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

In this section, we present the detailed theoretical analysis for the strong privacy preservation, strong security, accurate

reputation management, acceptable computation and communication overheads in the PPDR scheme, respectively.

A. Strong Privacy Preservation

In this part, we mainly analyze the PPDR scheme's privacy preservation ability for vehicle identity, LV-Reputation value, FV-Reputation value, and feedback score. The detailed analysis is as follows.

1) Vehicle Identity

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to reveal the vehicle V_i 's real identity OID_i . Suppose that the adversary \mathcal{A} is able to access the pseudonym $AID_i = \{AID_{i,1}, AID_{i,2}, T_i\}$ of vehicle V_i , where $AID_{i,1} = \alpha_i \cdot P$ with $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$, and $AID_{i,2} = OID_i \oplus h_1(SK_{TA} \cdot AID_{i,1} \parallel PK_{TA})$. Since the temporary private key of the vehicle is confidential, it is infeasible for \mathcal{A} to infer OID_i from $AID_{i,2}$.

2) Reputation Values

The reputation values include LV-reputation value and FV-reputation value. In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may seek to obtain the LV-Reputation value of a leading vehicle or the FV-Reputation value of a following vehicle. During the feedback score submission stage, the FV-Reputation value of each following vehicle (marked as V_i) is multiplied by its feedback score and encrypted by using the Paillier encryption. Without the Paillier private key (λ, μ) and the V_i 's feedback score x_k , the adversary cannot access the FV-Reputation value. Moreover, during the feedback score submission stage, the LV-Reputation value does not need to be transmitted. Additionally, in the reputation value update stage, both the LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value are updated by the TA which is honest, thus ensuring the LV-Reputation value privacy and the FV-Reputation value privacy.

3) Feedback Score

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to obtain the feedback score x_k submitted by the following vehicle V_i . Suppose that \mathcal{A} can access the encrypted data C_k and C'_k of V_i . However, in order to retrieve the feedback score x_k , \mathcal{A} must not only know the FV-Reputation value of V_i or the b_k value of entry certificate $P_{i,j,k}$, but also possess the Paillier private key (λ, μ) . Consequently, even if the CSP knows the b_k value of $P_{i,j,k}$, x_k still cannot be accessed without (λ, μ) . Furthermore, although the CSP can calculate the difference between the x_k and the incremental reputation value M_j , it cannot determine x_k since it has no knowledge of M_j .

B. Strong Security

In this part, we mainly demonstrate the strong security of the PPDR scheme against multiple common attacks, including the forgery attack, tampering attack, replay attack, and Sybil attack. The detailed analysis is as follows.

1) Forgery Attack

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to launch the FV-Reputation forgery attack by forging its FV-Reputation $r_{i,k}^F$ in C_k , to increase the weight of its feedback score. It is demonstrated that one-by-one verification in Eq. (8) can effectively counter this type of forgery attack. Concretely,

assume that \mathcal{A} can forge $r_{i,k}^F$ as $r_{i,k}^{F*}$. As a result, \mathcal{A} can forge C_k as $C_k^* = g^{x_k \cdot r_{i,k}^{F*}} \cdot (r_i)^n \bmod n^2$.

To enable C_k^* to pass the verification of Eq. (8), \mathcal{A} needs to correspondingly fake $\gamma_{i,j,k}$ as $\gamma_{i,j,k}^*$. Consequently, the CSP generates $R_{i,j,k}^* = Y_{i,j,k}^* \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}^*$, where $\eta_{i,j,k}^* = h_3(C_k^* \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4)$.

For \mathcal{A} to successfully launch the FV-Reputation forgery attack, C_k^* must pass the verification of Eq. (8), i.e., $\mu_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA} = h_2(AID_{i,k} \parallel PK_{TA}) \cdot P + PK_i + R_{i,j,k}$. By combining Eq. (8) and $R_{i,j,k} = Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}$, we can easily derive

$$\begin{aligned} & \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4) \\ &= \gamma_{i,j,k}^* \cdot h_3(C_k^* \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Due to the collision-resistant property of hash function [39], it can be concluded that \mathcal{A} is unable to generate C_k that satisfies the conditions of Eq. (21). Similarly, it can be readily proved that the batch verification in Eq. (10) is also resistant to the FV-Reputation forgery attack.

Furthermore, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to launch the pseudonym forgery attack by forging a pseudonym AID_i to decrease other vehicles' FV-Reputation values. It means that \mathcal{A} may attempt to forge $AID_{i,k}$ as $AID_{i,k}^*$, i.e. forge $P_{i,j,k} = (k, AID_{i,k}, AID_j, b_k)$ as $P_{i,j,k}^* = (k, AID_{i,k}^*, AID_j, b_k)$. It is demonstrated that one-by-one verification in Eq. (8) can effectively resist this type of forgery attack. To enable $AID_{i,k}^*$ to pass the verification of Eq. (8), \mathcal{A} needs to correspondingly fake $\gamma_{i,j,k}$ as $\gamma_{i,j,k}^*$. Consequently, the CSP generates $R_{i,j,k}^* = Y_{i,j,k}^* \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}^*$, where $\eta_{i,j,k}^* = h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k}^* \parallel t_4)$. By combining Eq. (8) and $R_{i,j,k} = Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}$, we can easily derive

$$\begin{aligned} & h_2(AID_{i,k} \parallel PK_{TA}) + Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k} \\ &= h_2(AID_{i,k}^* \parallel PK_{TA}) + Y_{i,j,k}^* \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}^*. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Based on the collision-resistant property of hash function [39], it can be inferred that \mathcal{A} is unable to generate $P_{i,j,k}$ that satisfies the conditions of Eq. (22). Similarly, it can be proved that the batch verification in Eq. (10) is resistant to the following vehicle's pseudonym forgery attack.

2) Tampering Attack

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may launch the feedback score tampering attack against another following vehicle V_i by modifying x_k to x_k^* , aiming to decrease V_i 's FV-Reputation value. However, x_k is not directly encrypted, and C_k and C_k' are calculated as $C_k = g^{x_k \cdot r_{i,k}^F} \cdot (r_i)^n \bmod n^2$ and $C_k' = g^{x_k \cdot b_k} \cdot (r_i')^n \bmod n^2$, respectively. Since \mathcal{A} has no access to $r_{i,k}^F$ and b_k , it cannot tamper with x_k to x_k^* such that the tampered $C_k^* = g^{x_k^* \cdot r_{i,k}^F} \cdot (r_i)^n \bmod n^2$ and $C_k' = g^{x_k^* \cdot b_k} \cdot (r_i')^n \bmod n^2$. Therefore, the PPDR scheme can resist the feedback score tampering attack.

In addition, the adversary \mathcal{A} may launch the leading vehicle's tampering attack against another leading vehicle V_j by modifying AID_j to AID_j^* , aiming to decrease V_j 's LV-Reputation value, i.e. tamper with $P_{i,j,k} = (k, AID_{i,k}, AID_j, b_k)$ to $P_{i,j,k}^* = (k, AID_{i,k}, AID_j^*, b_k)$. It is demonstrated that one-by-one verification in Eq. (8) can effectively resist the V_j 's pseudonym tampering attack. To

enable AID_j^* to pass the verification of Eq. (8), \mathcal{A} needs to alter $\gamma_{i,j,k}$ to $\gamma_{i,j,k}^*$. Consequently, the CSP generates $R_{i,j,k}^* = Y_{i,j,k}^* \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}^*$, where $\eta_{i,j,k}^* = h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k}^* \parallel t_4)$. By combining Eq. (8) and $R_{i,j,k} = Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}$, we can easily derive

$$\begin{aligned} & \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4) \\ &= \gamma_{i,j,k}^* \cdot h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k}^* \parallel t_4). \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Based on the collision-resistant property of hash function [39], it can be inferred that \mathcal{A} is unable to generate $P_{i,j,k}$ that satisfies the conditions of Eq. (23). Similarly, it can be proved that the batch verification in Eq. (10) is resistant to the following vehicle's pseudonym tampering attack.

3) Replay Attack

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to launch the replay attack by resubmitting M_4 . As described in Section V.F, M_4 with an expired t_4 cannot pass the timeliness verification of the CSP. Next, we prove that the one-by-one verification in Eq. (8) is resistant to the replay attack by modifying the t_4 . Assume that \mathcal{A} alters the expired t_4 to a current-time-valid t_4^* . Accordingly, \mathcal{A} would also need to modify $\gamma_{i,j,k}$ to $\gamma_{i,j,k}^*$. By combining Eq. (8) $Y_{i,j,k} = \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot PK_{TA}$, and $R_{i,j,k} = Y_{i,j,k} \cdot \eta_{i,j,k}$, we can easily derive

$$\begin{aligned} & \gamma_{i,j,k} \cdot h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4) \\ &= \gamma_{i,j,k}^* \cdot h_3(C_k \parallel C_k' \parallel P_{i,j,k} \parallel t_4^*). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Similar to the previous analysis, \mathcal{A} is unable to generate t_4 that satisfies the conditions of Eq. (24). We can easily prove that the batch verification in Eq. (10) is resistant to the replay attack. Besides, as described in Eq. (6), the CSP guarantees that each following vehicle can submit M_4 only once during its participation in the vehicle platoon. Overall, the PPDR scheme can resist the replay attack.

4) Sybil Attack

In the PPDR scheme, the adversary \mathcal{A} may attempt to carry out the Sybil attack by forging multiple pseudonym, temporary public key, and temporary private key. As analyzed in the forgery attack, \mathcal{A} cannot effectively generate pseudonym, temporary public key, and temporary private key that can pass signature verification. Consequently, \mathcal{A} cannot submit multiple M_4 for the same feedback target due to Eq. (7). Furthermore, the vehicle pseudonym is generated by the TA, and a vehicle is restricted to having a single pseudonym during each time interval. Therefore, the PPDR scheme can resist the Sybil attack.

C. Accurate Reputation Management

As indicated in Eq. (16), the incremental reputation value of each leading vehicle is essentially computed as the weighted average of corresponding following vehicles' feedback scores, with the corresponding FV-Reputation values serving as significant weights. As demonstrated in many recent researches [3], [15], the weighted average mechanism can achieve a substantially higher level of accuracy when compared to the simple average mechanism, and the quantitative accuracy evaluation is discussed in Section VII.C.

In addition, the dual reputation management mechanism is conducive to separate one vehicle's reputation value into LV-Reputation value and FV-Reputation value, thereby enhancing the accuracy of reputation management scheme, and the quantitative accuracy evaluation is discussed in Section VII.C.

D. Acceptable Computation Overhead

In this part, we analyze the computation overheads of various cryptographic operations on the TA, CSP, RSUs, and each following vehicle sides during the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages (note that, as these stages do not involve the leading vehicle, we do not take into account the computation overhead on the leading vehicle side). For the sake of simplicity, we assume there is one leading vehicle and v following vehicles, with the assumption that all the following vehicles participate in the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages.

Specifically, we denote the computation overheads of performing a Paillier modular exponentiation operation, a Paillier modular multiplication operation, a Paillier modular addition operation, an ECC modular multiplication operation, an ECC modular addition operation, an ECC point multiplication operation, an ECC modular exponentiation operation, an ECC modular subtraction operation, a Bilinear pairing operation, and a hash operation as T_P^e , T_P^m , T_P^a , T_E^m , T_E^a , T_E^p , T_E^e , T_E^s , T_e , and T_h , respectively. The detailed analysis is as follows.

Before submitting a feedback score x_k for the leading vehicle V_j , the following vehicle V_i is required to generate C_k and C'_k . The generation of C_k needs 1 Paillier modular exponential operation and 1 Paillier modular multiplication operation. Similarly, the generation of C'_k also needs 1 Paillier modular exponential operation and 1 Paillier modular multiplication operation. Additionally, to generate a signature $\sigma_{i,j,k}$, V_i needs to preforms 1 hash operations and 2 ECC modular addition operation. Consequently, the total computation overhead on each following vehicle side can be calculated as $2T_P^e + 2T_P^m + T_h + 2T_E^a$.

When the CSP receives all the M_4 from v following vehicles, it needs to verify the signatures. This can be accomplished through either one-by-one verification or batch verification.

- **One-by-One Verification:** For each M_4 , the CSP needs to execute 2 hash operations, 2 ECC modular multiplication operations, 1 ECC modular addition operations, and 1 ECC point multiplication operation.
- **Batch Verification:** To verify v M_4 , the CSP needs to execute $2v$ hash operations, $(v + 1)$ ECC modular multiplication operations, $(3v - 2)$ ECC modular addition operations, and 1 ECC point multiplication operation.

Subsequently, the CSP needs to calculate G_K^R and $G_K^{R'}$, which involves $2v$ Paillier modular multiplication operations. Therefore, the computation overhead on the CSP side is

- **One-by-One Verification:** $v \cdot (2T_h + 2T_E^m + T_E^a + T_E^p + 2T_P^m)$.
- **Batch Verification:** $2v \cdot T_h + (v + 1) \cdot T_E^m + (3v - 2)T_E^a + T_E^p + 2v \cdot T_P^m$.

The TA is required to perform 2 Paillier modular exponentiation operations and 2 Paillier modular multiplication operations. Hence, the computation overhead on the TA side can be calculated as $2(T_P^e + T_P^m)$.

In our PPDR scheme, RSUs function as relays, resulting in negligible computation overhead on their side.

To demonstrate the superiority of our PPDR scheme, we compare our PPDR scheme with other excellent schemes. Among these schemes, the RPPM [2], PPRU [3], and TPPR [14] schemes are the closest to ours, so we use them as the basis for theoretical analysis and simulation evaluation. To ensure a fair comparison, we make necessary adjustments to the RPPM, PPRU, and TPPR schemes. Moreover, in our PPDR scheme, we do not consider the update of the FV-Reputation value of each vehicle by the TA during the comparison, because the RPPM, PPRU, and TPPR schemes do not have the FV-Reputation value and therefore do not require such updates. Therefore, the computation overhead on the TA side in our PPDR scheme is reduced to $T_P^e + T_P^m$, while the other computation overheads remain unchanged. The computation overheads for each entity of the four our PPDR schemes are summarized in Table II, and the quantitative accuracy evaluation is discussed in Section VII.B.

E. Acceptable Communication Overhead

In this part, we analyze the communication overheads on the TA, CSP, RSUs, and each following vehicle sides during the feedback score submission and reputation value update stages (note that, as these stages do not involve the leading vehicle, we do not take into account the communication overhead on the leading vehicle side).

Specifically, we denote the bit lengths of the timestamp, ECC parameter q , ECC public key, Paillier parameter n^2 , hash value, AES ciphertext, order value k , b_k , and S_j as $|t|$, $|q|$, $|s|$, $|n^2|$, $|h|$, $|a|$, $|k|$, $|b|$, and $|j|$, respectively. The detailed analysis is as follows.

Each following vehicle needs to send the M_4 . Thus, the communication overhead on each following vehicle side can be calculated as $2|n^2| + 4|s| + 3|q| + 3|t| + |k| + |b|$.

The RSUs receive v M_4 from v following vehicles and subsequently forward these M_4 to the CSP. Consequently, the communication overhead on the RSUs side can be calculated as $2v \cdot (2|n^2| + 4|s| + 3|q| + 3|t| + |k| + |b|)$.

The CSP receives v M_4 , and then transmits the M_5 to the TA. The TA needs to receive the M_5 and send the S_j to the CSP. Finally, the CSP sends the M_6 to the TA. Thus, the communication overhead on the CSP side can be calculated as $v \cdot (2|n^2| + 4|s| + 3|q| + 3|t| + |k| + |b|) + 2|n^2| + |b| + (v + 1) \cdot (|s| + |q| + |t|) + |j| + v \cdot |E|$, and the communication overhead on the TA side can be calculated as $2|n^2| + |b| + (v + 1) \cdot (|s| + |q| + |t|) + |j| + v \cdot |E|$.

To demonstrate the superiority of our PPDR scheme, we compare our PPDR scheme with the RPPM [2], PPRU [3], and TPPR [14] schemes.

To ensure a fair comparison, we make necessary adjustments to the RPPM, PPRU, and TPPR schemes. Moreover, in our PPDR scheme, we do not consider the update of the

TABLE II: Computation overhead comparisons for each entity in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes.

Schemes	TA	CSP	RSUs	Each FV
RPPM [2]-one	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$v \cdot (T_E^p + T_h + T_E^m + T_E^a) + v \cdot T_P^e + 2(v-1) \cdot T_P^a$	0	$T_E^p + T_h + T_E^m + T_E^a$
RPPM [2]-batch	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$3v \cdot T_E^m + (3v-2) \cdot T_E^a + v \cdot T_h + T_E^p + v \cdot T_P^e + 2(v-1) \cdot T_P^a$	0	$T_E^p + T_h + T_E^m + T_E^a$
PPRU [3]-one	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$v \cdot (3T_P^e + 3T_P^m + 4T_h + 2T_E^p + T_E^a) + 2(v-1) \cdot T_P^a$	0	$2T_P^e + T_P^m + T_h + T_E^m + 2T_E^a + T_E^p$
PPRU [3]-batch	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$4T_P^e + 3T_P^m + (v+3) \cdot T_h + T_E^a + 3T_E^p + (2v-1) \cdot T_E^a + (2v-1) \cdot T_E^m$	0	$2T_P^e + T_P^m + T_h + T_E^m + 2T_E^a + T_E^p$
TPPR [14]-one	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$2T_e + v \cdot T_h$	$v \cdot (4T_e + 4T_h + 2T_E^m + T_E^a + T_P^e + 2T_P^e) + (2v-1) \cdot T_E^a$	$3T_P^e + 3T_P^m + 4T_h + 2T_E^a + 2T_E^m$
TPPR [14]-batch	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m$	$2T_e + v \cdot T_h$	$4T_e + (8v-7) \cdot T_E^a + (v+3)T_h + (2v+1) \cdot T_E^m + 2T_P^e + (v+1) \cdot T_P^e$	$3T_P^e + 3T_P^m + 4T_h + 2T_E^a + 2T_E^m$
PPDR-one	$T_P^e + T_P^m$	$v \cdot (2T_h + 2T_E^m + 1T_E^a + T_E^p + 2T_P^m)$	0	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m + 2T_h + T_E^a$
PPDR-batch	$T_P^e + T_P^m$	$2v \cdot T_h + (v+1) \cdot T_E^m + (3v-2) \cdot T_E^a + T_P^e + 2v \cdot T_P^m$	0	$2T_P^e + 2T_P^m + 2T_h + T_E^a$

Note: 1) RPPM-one and RPPM-batch denote the RPPM scheme with one-by-one verification and with batch verification, respectively.
2) PPRU-one and PPRU-batch denote the PPRU scheme with one-by-one verification and with batch verification, respectively.
3) TPPR-one and TPPR-batch denote the TPPR scheme with one-by-one verification and with batch verification, respectively.
4) PPDR-one and PPDR-batch denote our PPDR scheme with one-by-one verification and with batch verification, respectively.

TABLE III: Communication overhead comparisons for each entity in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes.

Schemes	TA	CSP	RSUs	Each FV
RPPM [2]	$2 q + 2 n^2 $	$v \cdot (3 q + t) + 2 q + 2 n^2 $	$2v \cdot (3 q + t)$	$3 q + t $
PPRU [3]	$ t + s + 2 n^2 $	$v \cdot (t + 3 s + 3 n^2 + q) + t + s + 2 n^2 $	$2v \cdot (t + 3 s + 3 n^2 + q)$	$ t + 3 s + 3 n^2 + q $
TPPR [14]	$2 n^2 $	$ a + 2 n^2 + v \cdot a + q + 2 n^2 $	$v \cdot t + 2(v+1) \cdot n^2 + (3v+1) \cdot a + (2v+1) \cdot q $	$2 a + 2 n^2 + t + 2 q $
PPDR	$2 n^2 + b + (v+1) \cdot (s + q + t) + j $	$v \cdot (2 n^2 + 4 s + 3 q + 3 t + k + b) + 2 n^2 + b + (v+1) \cdot (s + q + t) + j $	$2v \cdot (2 n^2 + 4 s + 3 q + 3 t + k + b)$	$2 n^2 + 4 s + 3 q + 3 t + k + b $

FV-Reputation value of each vehicle by the TA during the comparison, because the RPPM, PPRU, and TPPR schemes do not have the FV-Reputation value and therefore do not require such updates. Therefore, the communication overhead on the TA side in our PPDR scheme is reduced to $2|n^2| + |b| + (v+1) \cdot (|s| + |q| + |t|) + |j|$, the communication overhead on the CSP side in our PPDR scheme is reduced to $v \cdot (2|n^2| + 4|s| + 3|q| + 3|t| + |k| + |b|) + 2|n^2| + |b| + (v+1) \cdot (|s| + |q| + |t|) + |j|$, while the other communication overheads remain unchanged. The communication overheads for each entity in the four schemes are summarized in Table III. Additionally, we set the parameters as shown in Table IV, and the quantitative communication overhead comparisons on the TA, CSP, RSUs, and each following vehicle sides are depicted in Fig. 3, where v ranges from 1 to 10.

TABLE IV: Parameter setting in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes.

Parameters	Definitions	Bit lengths
$ t $	Bit length of the timestamp	32
$ q $	Bit length of the ECC parameter q	128
$ s $	Bit length of the ECC public key	256
$ n^2 $	Bit length of the Paillier parameter n^2	2048
$ h $	Bit length of the hash value	20
$ a $	Bit length of the AES ciphertext	128
$ k $	Bit length of the order value k	4
$ b $	Bit length of the b_k	8
$ j $	Bit length of the S_j	8

Fig. 3 shows the variations of the communication overheads

on the TA, CSP, RSUs, and each following vehicle sides in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes as v increases. Although the communication overheads of the four entities in our PPDR scheme are higher than that in the RPPM and TPPR schemes, respectively, and the communication overhead on the TA side is higher than that in the PPRU scheme, it can be seen from Table I that in addition to preserving the reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, our PPDR scheme improves the accuracy of reputation management scheme by adopting the weighted average mechanism and the dual reputation management mechanism.

F. Algorithm Correctness Proof

We employ mathematical induction to prove that the algorithm correctly computes the sequence $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K\}$, satisfying the Eq. (25).

$$D_k = x_{\max} - M_j + x_k, \forall k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}. \quad (25)$$

1) Base Case

For $K = 1$, the algorithm initializes $s_1 = S_j$ and iteratively computes Eq. (26).

$$D_1 = \frac{s_1}{b_1}. \quad (26)$$

Given the Eq.(18), the S_1 can be calculated as Eq. (27).

$$S_1 = \sum_{k=1}^K b_k \cdot (x_{\max} - M_j + x_k) = b_1 \cdot (x_{\max} - M_j + x_k). \quad (27)$$

Fig. 3: Communication overhead comparisons on (a) TA, (b) CSP, (c) RSUs, and (d) each following vehicle sides in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes.

Therefore, the Eq. (28) can be calculated.

$$D_1 = \frac{s_1}{b_1} = \frac{b_1 \cdot (x_{\max} - M_j + x_k)}{b_1} = x_{\max} - M_j + x_k. \quad (28)$$

Obviously, this result is consistent with the target equation, so the basic case holds.

2) Inductive Hypothesis

Assume that for $K = m$, the algorithm correctly computes the Eq. (29).

$$D_k = x_{\max} - M_j + x_k, \forall k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}. \quad (29)$$

3) Inductive Step

For $K = m + 1$, the algorithm initializes $s_{m+1} = S_j$ and iteratively computes the Eq. (30) and Eq. (31).

$$s_m = s_{m+1} \pmod{b_{m+1}}, \quad (30)$$

$$D_{m+1} = \frac{s_{m+1} - s_m}{b_{m+1}}. \quad (31)$$

According to the induction hypothesis, for all $k \leq m$, there are

$$s_k = \sum_{n=1}^k b_n (x_{\max} - M_j + x_n). \quad (32)$$

Thus, for $k = m + 1$,

$$s_{m+1} - s_m = b_{m+1} (x_{\max} - M_j + x_{m+1}). \quad (33)$$

Divide both sides by b_{m+1} to get the Eq. (34).

$$D_{m+1} = x_{\max} - M_j + x_{m+1}. \quad (34)$$

By the principle of mathematical induction, the algorithm correctly computes $D_k = x_{\max} - M_j + x_k$ for all $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, thereby proving its correctness.

VII. SIMULATION EVALUATION

In this section, we first introduce the simulation settings, then compare the computation overhead in the PPDR scheme with that in the RPPM [2], PPRU [3], and TPPR [14] schemes. Afterwards, by comparing with the simple average mechanism and the single reputation management mechanism, we demonstrate that adopting the weighted average mechanism and the dual reputation management mechanism can significantly improve the accuracy of reputation management scheme.

A. Simulation Settings

The simulation is carried out on a notebook computer equipped with 12th Gen Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-1240p1.70ghz and 16G memory. The operating platform is 64-bit Windows 11. The simulation of cryptographic operation adopts Java Pairing-Based Cryptography (JPBC) library¹.

B. Computation Overhead Evaluation

In this part, we first measure the runtimes of various cryptographic operations for 1000 times, respectively, and the average results are presented in Table V. Specifically, we calculate the computation overheads on the TA, CSP, RSUs, and each following vehicle sides in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes when v varies from 1 to 10. The results are illustrated in Fig. 4.

TABLE V: Runtimes (MS) of various cryptographic operations in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR, and our PPDR schemes.

Notations	Definitions	Runtimes
T_P^e	Time of a Paillier modular exponential operation	1.21315
T_P^m	Time of a Paillier modular multiplication operation	0.01086
T_P^a	Time of a Paillier modular addition operation	0.00177
T_E^m	Time of an ECC modular multiplication operation	1.56896
T_E^a	Time of an ECC modular addition operation	0.00509
T_E^b	Time of an ECC point multiplication operation	0.00809
T_E^e	Time of an ECC modular exponential operation	0.00780
T_E^s	Time of an ECC modular subtraction operation	0.00125
T_e	Time of a bilinear pairing operation	3.79000
T_h	Time of a hash operation	0.00106

As depicted in Fig. 4(a), the computation overhead on the TA side in our PPDR scheme is significantly lower than that in the other three schemes, indicating that our PPDR scheme can notably decrease the computation overhead on the TA side. Specifically, when compared with the RPPM, PPRU, and TPPR schemes, the computation overhead on the TA side in our PPDR scheme is reduced by 50%.

As depicted in Fig. 4(b), for most values of v (i.e., $v > 3$), when the one-by-one verification is adopted, the computation overhead on the CSP side in our PPDR scheme is lower than that in the PPRU scheme, but higher than that in the RPPM and TPPR schemes; when the batch verification is adopted,

¹<http://gas.dia.unisa.it/projects/jpbc/>.

Fig. 4: Computation overhead comparisons on (a) TA, (b) CSP, (c) RSUs, and (d) each following vehicle sides in the RPPM, PPRU, TPPR and our PPDR schemes.

the computation overhead in our PPDR scheme is lower than that in the RPPM and PPRU schemes, but higher than that in the TPPR scheme. Note that in practice, the CSP often has powerful computational capabilities, and thus the computation overhead on the CSP side in our PPDR scheme is acceptable. Furthermore, as indicated in Table I, our PPDR scheme not only achieves the dual reputation management mechanism and the weighted average mechanism, but also preserves the reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, which is not achieved by the other three schemes.

In addition, in our PPDR scheme, for each v , when the batch verification is adopted, the computation overhead on the CSP side is lower than that when the one-by-one verification is adopted. Therefore, the batch verification can effectively reduce the computation overhead on the CSP side than the one-by-one verification.

As depicted in Fig. 4(c), for each v , regardless of whether the batch verification or the one-by-one verification is adopted, the computation overhead on the RSUs side in our PPDR scheme is 0, the same as that in the RPPM and PPRU schemes, and is significantly lower than that in the TPPR scheme.

As depicted in Fig. 4(d), the computation overhead on each following vehicle side in our PPDR scheme is slightly higher than that in the RPPM scheme, and significantly lower than that in the PPRU and TPPR schemes. Moreover, it can be seen from Table I that in addition to preserving the reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, our PPDR scheme improves the accuracy of reputation management by adopting the weighted average mechanism and the dual reputation management mechanism.

C. Accuracy Reputation Management Evaluation

1) Parameter Settings

In this part, we consider two types of vehicle platoons. The first type has an honest leading vehicle, while the second type has a malicious leading vehicle. Each vehicle platoon consists of 1 leading vehicle and 100 following vehicles. Assume that two types of leading vehicles are private vehicles. Based on Eq. (3), the initial LV-Reputation value of each leading vehicle is set as $[0.1 \cdot \eta_1]$.

The initial FV-Reputation value of each following vehicle is set according to Eq. (4). Specifically, we assume there are 1000 following vehicles, which are composed of 5% law enforcement vehicles, 10% public service vehicles, and 85% private vehicles. For the sake of simplicity, we categorize the following vehicles into two types, namely honest following vehicles and malicious following vehicles. Law enforcement vehicles and public service vehicles are regarded as honest following vehicles, while private vehicles may be malicious following vehicles. Inspired by the previous works [3], [15], [34], [40], we adjust the percentage of malicious vehicles in private vehicles, denoted as $P_m \in \{10\%, 20\%, 30\%, 40\%\}$. Then we adopt three common evaluation indexes, namely the average FV-Reputation value of honest following vehicles (denoted as R_h^F), the average FV-Reputation value of malicious following vehicles (denoted as R_m^F), and the LV-Reputation value of each leading vehicle (denoted as R^L). For each P_m , we conduct FV-Reputation value update in the PPDR scheme for 100 rounds, with the serial number of each round (denoted as R_n) being 1, 2, \dots , or 100.

To simulate real-world conditions, we assume that the feedback scores are generated by randomly sampling the real numbers within the range of $[\mu - 5\% \cdot \eta_2, \mu + 5\% \cdot \eta_2]$, following the normal distribution $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ as [41]

$$f(x|\mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (35)$$

where μ represents the mean, and σ represents the standard deviation. When the leading vehicle and the following vehicle are both honest vehicles or both malicious vehicles, $\mu = \mu_1$. Otherwise, $\mu = \mu_2$. Note that $\mu_1 > \mu_2$.

Inspired by [2], [3], [15], we assume that $\sigma = 2$, $\eta_1 = 100$, $\eta_2 = 100$, $th_1 = 5$, $th_2 = 15$, $x_{max} = 100$, $\rho = 0.9$, $\mu_1 = 85$, and $\mu_2 = 35$.

2) Weighted Average Mechanism Versus Simple Average Mechanism

To demonstrate the advantages of the weighted average mechanism, we evaluate reputation value update in the PPDR scheme when the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the results when the leading vehicle is honest and malicious, respectively.

When the leading vehicle is honest, Fig. 5 shows how R_h^F , R_m^F , and R^L change with R_n when the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted. As depicted in Fig. 5(a), when the weighted average mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , as R_n increases, R_h^F increases until it reaches 100. However, when the simple average mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$, R_h^F increases, but the growth rate

is significantly slower than that when the weighted average mechanism is adopted. Moreover, for $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, or $P_m = 40\%$, R_h^F decreases until it reaches 0, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. As depicted in Fig. 5(b), for each P_m , regardless of whether the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted, R_m^F decreases until it reaches 0. As depicted in Fig. 5(c), when the weighted average mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , R^L increases until it finally approaches 80. When the simple average mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$, R^L increases until it finally approaches 75. However, for $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, or $P_m = 40\%$, R^L initially increases in the first 10 rounds but then declines in the subsequent rounds, eventually reaching 0, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. Therefore, when the leading vehicle is honest, the weighted average mechanism generally provides higher accuracy of reputation management scheme than the simple average mechanism.

When the leading vehicle is malicious, Fig. 6 shows how R_h^F , R_m^F , and R^L change with R_n when the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted. As depicted in Fig. 6(a), when the weighted average mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , as P_m increases, R_h^F increases until it reaches 100. When the simple average mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$ or $P_m = 20\%$, R_h^F increases until it reaches 100, but for $P_m = 30\%$ or $P_m = 40\%$, R_h^F decreases until it reaches 0, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. As depicted in Fig. 6(b), for each P_m , regardless of whether the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted, R_m^F decreases until it reaches 0. As depicted in Fig. 6(c), when the weighted average mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , R^L increases until it finally approaches 30. When the simple average mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$ or $P_m = 20\%$, R^L increases until it approaches 25. However, for $P_m = 30\%$ or $P_m = 40\%$, R^L initially increases in the first 10 rounds but then declines in the subsequent rounds, eventually reaching 0, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. Therefore, when the leading vehicle is malicious, the weighted average mechanism generally provides higher accuracy of reputation management scheme than the simple average mechanism.

3) Dual Reputation Management Mechanism Versus Single Reputation Management Mechanism

To demonstrate the advantages of the dual reputation management mechanism, we evaluate reputation value update in the PPDR scheme when the dual average mechanism or the single average mechanism is adopted. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the results when the leading vehicle is honest and malicious, respectively.

When the leading vehicle is honest, Fig. 7 shows how R_h^F , R_m^F , and R^L change with R_n when the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted. As depicted in Fig. 7(a), when the dual reputation management mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , as R_n increases, R_h^F increases until it reaches 100. When the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$, R_h^F increases with R_n until it reaches 100, and for $P_m = 20\%$ or $P_m = 30\%$, R_h^F first decreases and then increases, ultimately reaching 100. However, for

$P_m = 40\%$, R_h^F continuously decreases and eventually reaches 0, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. As depicted in Fig. 7(b), when the dual reputation management mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , R_m^F decreases until it reaches 0. When the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, or $P_m = 30\%$, R_m^F decreases until it reaches 0. However, for $P_m = 40\%$, R_m^F decreases in the first 40 rounds, but then increases in the subsequent rounds, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. As illustrated in Fig. 7(c), when the dual reputation management mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , R^L continually increases and finally approaches 80. When the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, or $P_m = 30\%$, R^L continually increases and finally approaches 80. However, for $P_m = 40\%$, R^L increases in the first 40 rounds, but then decreases in the subsequent rounds, and finally approaches 30, which is clearly an unfavorable outcome. Therefore, when the leading vehicle is honest, the dual reputation management generally provides higher accuracy of reputation management scheme than the single reputation management mechanism.

When the leading vehicle is malicious, Fig. 8 shows how R_h^F , R_m^F , and R^L change with R_n when the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted. As depicted in Fig. 8(a), when the dual reputation management mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , as R_n increases, R_h^F increases until it eventually reaches 100. When the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, for $P_m = 10\%$ or $P_m = 20\%$, R_h^F increases until it reaches 100. However, for $P_m = 30\%$ or $P_m = 40\%$, R_h^F first decreases and then increases, but ultimately fails to reach 100. As depicted in Fig. 8(b), for each P_m , regardless of whether the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, R_m^F decreases until it reaches 0. As depicted in Fig. 8(c), regardless of whether the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted, for each P_m , R^L increases until it approaches 30. Therefore, when the leading vehicle is malicious, the dual reputation management generally provides higher accuracy of reputation management scheme than the single reputation management mechanism.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose the PPDR management scheme for vehicle platoon. Specifically, we first introduce the single reputation attack. To resist this attack, the PPDR scheme employs a dual reputation management mechanism. Furthermore, under the premise of preserving reputation value privacy, feedback score privacy, and identity privacy, the PPDR scheme employs a score difference calculation algorithm to support the weighted average mechanism and the dual reputation management mechanism. Additionally, comprehensive theoretical analysis demonstrates that the PPDR scheme can provide strong privacy preservation and strong security with acceptable computation and communication overheads. Simulation results indicate that the PPDR scheme is significantly superior than the existing schemes in several aspects.

In future work, we aim to further optimize the PPDR scheme to offer additional functionalities. Furthermore, we

Fig. 5: Variation curve comparisons of (a) R_h^F , (b) R_m^F , and (c) R^L with an honest leading vehicle when the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted (where 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% are short for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, and $P_m = 40\%$, respectively; WA and SA are short for the weighted average mechanism and the simple average mechanism, respectively).

Fig. 6: Variation curve comparisons of (a) R_h^F , (b) R_m^F , and (c) R^L with a malicious leading vehicle when the weighted average mechanism or the simple average mechanism is adopted (where 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% are short for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, and $P_m = 40\%$, respectively; WA and SA are short for the weighted average mechanism and the simple average mechanism, respectively).

Fig. 7: Variation curve comparisons of (a) R_h^F , (b) R_m^F , and (c) R^L with an honest leading vehicle when the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted (where 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% are short for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, and $P_m = 40\%$, respectively; DR and SR are short for the dual reputation management mechanism and the single reputation management mechanism, respectively).

Fig. 8: Variation curve comparisons of (a) R_h^F , (b) R_m^F , and (c) R^L with a malicious leading vehicle when the dual reputation management mechanism or the single reputation management mechanism is adopted (where 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% are short for $P_m = 10\%$, $P_m = 20\%$, $P_m = 30\%$, and $P_m = 40\%$, respectively; DR and SR are short for the dual reputation management mechanism and the single reputation management mechanism, respectively).

plan to integrate blockchain technology into a distributed vehicle platoon management scheme.

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